

IDENTIFICATION OF EFFECTOR PROTEINS DURING INTERACTION OF MUSHROOM-FORMING FUNGI WITH THEIR COMPETITORS

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Mushroom-forming fungi are prone to pests and diseases, which can lead to devastating crop losses. To counteract predation, fungi have evolved several methods to defend themselves, including the secretion of effector proteins. However, few secreted proteins involved in defence have been identified in mushroom-forming fungi.

To elucidate the secreted arsenal of mushroom-forming fungi against their competitors, we determined gene expression during interactions between vegetative mycelium of the mushroom-forming fungus *Schizophyllum commune* and four fungal or bacterial competitors. Additionally, RNA-seq was performed on the mushroom-forming fungus *Pleurotus ostreatus* against a fungal competitor to study conserved defence responses.

Upregulation of transcripts encoding thaumatins and glycosyl hydrolases were observed as the main annotated groups for putative secreted proteins in *S. commune*, whereas redox-related proteins were predominantly present during interaction in *P. ostreatus*. However, most drastic changes in expression were observed in unannotated genes, which lack known domains. Moreover, there was a conserved response, since 31 and 21 orthologous secreted proteins of *S. commune* and *P. ostreatus*, respectively, showed a similar expression profile during interaction. These orthologues are all widely conserved among fungi.

The gene encoding the small secreted protein Tip1 was strongly upregulated during interaction, and we studied this gene in more detail. A reporter strain was generated by placing the red fluorescent dTomato gene under the control of the tip1 promoter. No fluorescence was observed during mono-cultivation, whereas strong fluorescence was only found during interaction. Furthermore, Tip1 was heterologously expressed and purified to analyse its function. Tip1 inhibited growth of fungal competitors, although its exact function is still unknown. Further investigation of function and regulatory network will contribute to the understandings of the defence system of mushroom-forming fungi.

EXPLORING THE DIVERGENCE OF FUNCTIONAL AND EVOLUTIONAL INTERACTIONS BETWEEN FUNGI AND BACTERIA

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Fungi and bacteria comprise a large fraction of biomass in the soil and bacterial-fungal interactions are crucial for understanding the microbial ecosystem which is closely related to agriculture, medicine and the environment. The interactions between microbes promote the activation of cryptic biosynthetic pathways that produces secondary metabolites and other bioactive compounds that drive interactive dynamics.

Our recent study described the distinctive nature of the mutualistic relationship between the filamentous fungus *Aspergillus nidulans* and gram-positive bacterium *Bacillus subtilis* depicting evidence to show their spatial and metabolic interactions that facilitates the communication in between species to explore untraversed environmental niches and obtain nutrients. Confronting this interactive nature, the current study was comprised of co-culturing of 36 environmental fungal species and 22 bacterial species to further investigate the interaction dynamics in the co-cultures. Parameters such as the effect on the fungal growth, the affinity of the bacterial cells to the fungal hyphae, bacterial cell dispersal distance and the velocity of movement of bacteria were analyzed to define the phenotypic interaction specificity. Depending on the nature of interactions, the combinations were then classified into genres of positive, negative, and neutral. In depth analysis of the diversity of interaction specificity even among the species of *Aspergillus* species with *Bacillus subtilis* revealed that specific antagonism demonstrated in *Aspergillus niger* was directed primarily through Pyranonigrin A. Subsequently, selected combinations were subjected to LCMS/MS analysis and transcriptomic analysis to visualize their genomic potential and expression in coexistence compared to their monoculture state which would assist in defining the factors that help establish and maintain the relationships of the microbes in the microbial network setting.

This study intended to impart insights to the ecological context of interactions of the environmental microbiota and utilization of the metabolic capacity of the chemically prolific microorganisms.

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A CARNIVOROUS MUSHROOM PARALYZES AND KILLS NEMATODES VIA A VOLATILE KETONE

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Fungal predatory behavior on nematodes has evolved independently in several lineages. *Pleurotus ostreatus*, the basidiomycete oyster mushroom, is a nematophagous fungus that preys on nematodes when limited nutrients are available. Our previous study showed that when *Caenorhabditis elegans* contacted the mycelium of *P. ostreatus*, the toxins could enter through cilia, causing head muscle hyper-contraction and calcium influx in pharyngeal and body wall muscles, finally resulting in the necrosis process. However, the molecular identity of the nematode-paralyzing toxins produced by *P. ostreatus* remained unclear. To study this question, we conducted random mutagenesis forward genetic screens in *P. ostreatus* to isolate mutants that were unable to paralyze *C. elegans*. We generated ~12,000 UV and EMS-mutagenized clones and identified 22 *P. ostreatus* loss-of-toxicity (lot) mutants that lacked nematocidal activity toward *C. elegans*. Viewing the morphology of the lot mutants revealed that they all lack the spherical structures, toxocysts, on the hyphae. Toxocysts are fragile and lose nematocidal activity easily. Therefore, we hypothesized that toxins inside toxocysts are volatile. We conducted GC-MS and identified 3-octanone as a promising candidate for the nematocidal compound. 3-octanone treatment recapitulated the phenotypes of rapid calcium influx and neuronal cell death by targeting the cell membrane and disrupting membrane integrity *in vivo* and *in vitro* to trigger rapid cell death in *C. elegans*. Our work reveals that *P. ostreatus* develops a specific structure to concentrate a volatile ketone to disrupt the membrane integrity of *C. elegans*, resulting in rapid organismal cell death.